

D5.1

PoDIUM evaluation methodology

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AD	Autonomous Driving
ADAS	Automated Driving Assistance System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
C-ACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transportation System
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-everything
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CI	Confidence Interval
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CRE	Collision Risk Estimator
CV	Connected Vehicle
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DT	Digital Twin
EU-CEM	European Common Evaluation Methodology
EV	Emergency Vehicle
FOT	Field Operational Test
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMI	Human Machine Interface
ICT	Information and communications technology
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LL	Living Lab

Abbreviation	Meaning
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
OBU	On-Board Unit
O-D	Origin-Destination
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SIA	Software Integrity Architecture
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TC	Test Case
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TMS	Traffic Management System
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
UC	Use Case
V2I	Vehicle-to-infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle-to-vehicle
VIMA	VRU Intersection Movement Assist
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

Executive Summary

The main objective of PoDIUM is to demonstrate and validate the applicability and benefits of connected and cooperative automated mobility (CCAM) in real traffic conditions. To achieve this, the facilities of three well-equipped living labs in Germany, Italy and Spain will be used. A rich set of demanding CCAM use cases will be investigated to identify and assess all the connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs that will allow the proposed higher levels of automation.

The present document is the deliverable D5.1 “PoDIUM evaluation methodology”. It has been developed by task T5.1 “Evaluation methodology and plan”. The main objective of the deliverable is to provide a common evaluation methodology to be used to test and evaluate the PoDIUM platform and the use cases. The methodology is composed of a technical evaluation part and a user acceptance evaluation part.

The PoDIUM platform will be technically evaluated with seven test cases, that cover KPIs from five categories according to 5G-PPP’s second white paper about KPIs: service availability, latency, compute, service reliability and security. The use case test cases cover functional aspects leading to Pass and Fail verdicts based on the expected behaviour.

In addition to the technical evaluation aspects, which provide the grounds for task T5.2 “UCs technical evaluation and LL demonstration activities”, the public acceptance evaluation methodology is also defined in the present deliverable. This methodology, based on surveys tailored for different stakeholder groups, will act as base for task 5.3 “Public acceptance and impact assessment”.

The present deliverable has been developed in cooperation with all WP5 partners before starting the actual tests. The implementation of the described methodology in the future may lead to further refinements of the methodology which will be reported in subsequent WP5 deliverables.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the PDI system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New C-ITS messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of the present deliverable is to describe the evaluation methodology to be used in PoDIUM. This includes the technical evaluation of the PoDIUM platform and the use cases, and the user acceptance evaluation.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is “public” (PU). It is primarily aimed to be the reference document to be used by the PoDIUM Consortium Members during the evaluation phases of the project. Furthermore, this deliverable is addressed to any interested reader (i.e., public dissemination level) who wants to be informed about PoDIUM’s evaluation methodology.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable is organized as follows:

- Section 2 reviews the evaluation methodologies used in similar previous projects.
- Section 3 describes the technical evaluation methodology.
- Section 4 describes the tests cases planned to evaluate the PoDIUM platform.
- Section 5 describes the tests cases planned to evaluate the PoDIUM use cases.
- Section 6 describes the user acceptance evaluation methodology.
- Section 7 concludes the document with some insights.

For the convenience of the reader, the present deliverable D5.1 includes an annex with an updated version of PoDIUM’s KPIs. The initial version of the KPIs were included in the deliverable D2.3.

2. Overview of evaluation methodologies

This section reviews the evaluation methodologies used in similar European CCAM projects or proposed by European initiatives related to C-ITS and CCAM. Then, the applicability of the reviewed methodologies in the context of PoDIUM is discussed and some conclusions are extracted after looking at the advantages and disadvantages of each option.

2.1. FESTA

The Field Operational Test support Action (FESTA) methodology highlights the main activities to be carried in order to complete a “Field Operational Test” defined as “a study undertaken to evaluate a function, or functions, under normal operating conditions in road traffic environments, typically encountered by the participants using study design to identify real-world effects and benefits” [1].

The FESTA methodology identifies three main areas of intervention, broken down into several subtasks and organizes them in the so-called “V shape”. The first area of activities, called “Preparing,” includes all tasks aimed at identifying the functions to be tested, the use cases identified for testing these functions, as well as the research questions, hypotheses, and corresponding KPIs. The second area, called “Using,” encompasses activities related to identifying guidelines for storing the collected data and the tools for data analysis. The third area, “Analysing,” involves all activities related to testing the predefined hypotheses, focusing on providing unit values for the impacts of each test. A transversal element, named “Context,” underscores the need for a clearly defined set of information about the surrounding environment where the field tests will take place.

The original document and its first update (Version 2) were produced by the FESTA project consortium in 2008. Since the FESTA project, the handbook was maintained and updated by FOT-Net, a networking operation open to anyone interested in FOTs and run by the following European Support Actions: FOT-Net (2008–2010), FOT-Net 2 (2011–2013) and FOT-Net Data (2014–2016). In 2016, FOT-Net merged with another EU-funded support action, VRA (Vehicle Road Automation), to form a new networking forum and to coordinate automated road transport research projects. This collaboration has so far resulted in two new support actions: CARTRE (2016–2018) and ARCADE (2018–2021). These projects have compiled the latest two updates of this handbook. In August 2021, ARCADE published Micro-FESTA [2], a condensed evaluation methodology to support small pilot projects of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). This document gives an overview of the main steps in the FESTA methodology and comments their role in small-scale testing. This document can also be used as a first introduction to the full FESTA methodology and available materials.

2.2. C-ROADS

Through the C-Roads Platform, authorities and road operators join to harmonise the deployment activities of cooperative intelligent transport systems (C-ITS) across Europe. The goal is to achieve the deployment of interoperable cross-border C-ITS services for road users. The C-Roads Platform is steered by the C-Roads Steering Committee which is composed by Member State representatives. Within C-Roads, Pilots will evaluate the impacts of Day 1 C-ITS Services and Use Cases implemented

during the different Pilot Tests with respect of the following impact areas [3]: user acceptance, functional evaluation, safety, traffic efficiency, environment and socio-economic.

2.3. ICT4CART

ICT4CART was a Horizon 2020 project that run between September 2018 and February 2022. ICT4CART provided an ICT infrastructure to enable the transition towards road transport automation. The ICT4CART's defined a technical evaluation framework [4], that required the definition of KPIs using a common KPI template with the following fields: "description", "where to measure", "how to measure" and "comments". The traffic flow of the evaluation messaging was also defined describing the point of observation, the communication protocol, the logging frequency and other relevant logging information. The methodology also included user acceptance and impact assessment.

2.4. 5G-MOBIX

5G-MOBIX was a Horizon 2020 project that run between November 2018 and September 2022, which studied the added value of 5G connectivity for connected and automated mobility services and functionalities in cross-border conditions. The 5G-MOBIX evaluation methodology split the evaluation into three parts: Technical Evaluation, Impact Assessment, and User Acceptance [5]. The Technical Evaluation was tailored to the scope of the project, which was assessing the 5G capabilities for CCAM in a cross-border context. The KPI definition template was the same one used in ICT4CART. The user acceptance methodology was very comprehensive and employed five KPIs (perceived usefulness, trust, reliability, perceived ease-of-use and intention to use) and collected data from controlled trials, online interviews, real-world trials and user surveys.

2.5. 5G-IANA

5G-IANA is an ongoing Horizon project that started on June 2021 and is planned to end in November 2024. The 5G-IANA evaluation work is structured in a very similar way to PoDIUM in terms of objectives, tasks and deliverables. The 5G-IANA's technical evaluation methodology uses a similar KPI template than ICT4CART or 5G-MOBIX with the addition of the "how to evaluate" field [6], which describes the comparison approach (i.e. what values the measured KPI data points are compared to). The same KPI definition template was adopted in PoDIUM as explained in the deliverable D2.3 [7]. In contrast to ICT4CART, 5G-IANA's technical evaluation methodology includes the definition of test cases, which is a common practice in standard development organization (SDOs) such as 3GPP (see for instance [8]). The user acceptance methodology is based on the one from 5G-MOBIX but adapted to the objectives and scope of 5G-IANA.

2.6. FAME

The FAME project is developing a European Common Evaluation Methodology (EU-CEM) for CCAM that provides guidance on how to set up and carry out an evaluation or assessment of direct and indirect (wider socio-economic) impacts directed to different user groups. EU-CEM is part of European framework for CCAM testing on public roads. The FAME project started on July 2022 and will end in June 2025. FAME builds on previous projects: EU-funded Coordination and Support Actions ARCADE,

CARTRE, VRA, FOT-Net, and FESTA (2007-2008). The first draft of EU-CEM was published in May 2024 [9]. The overall scope of this handbook is to provide guidelines and share best practices for planning and conducting CCAM evaluation, especially impact assessment.

2.7. Overview conclusions

The FESTA methodology has been a reference evaluation methodology in automotive projects. However, it was designed for products which can be used by ordinary drivers over long periods of time in their daily lives [9], which goes some steps further in technology maturity level compared to PoDIUM. FESTA is trying to address this gap developing a methodology that can be used in CCAM innovation projects with immature technologies that are tested in the real world. However, the work is still ongoing and the first draft of the methodology was published just one month before the delivery deadline of the present PoDIUM deliverable D5.1. By the time of publication, the PoDIUM consortium had already defined the methodology and was finalising the present deliverable D5.1. In addition, the draft FESTA methodology includes a vast number of guidelines, what makes its complete application too complex for a project like PoDIUM. In any case, the PoDIUM consortium will look into the FESTA methodology with more detail to extract valid ideas that could be incorporated to the execution of the tests and the analysis of results. C-ROADS is another big initiative at European level that published its own methodology. In this case, the focus was on evaluating the socio-economic impacts of Day 1 C-ITS Services and Use Cases, which is not exactly the scope of PoDIUM.

Three European CCAM projects have been identified as more appropriate for taking as a reference in PoDIUM: ICT4CAR, 5G-MOBIX and 5G-IANA. The KPI definition template was originally proposed in ICT4CAR, adopted in 5G-MOBIX and extended in 5G-IANA. The one used in PoDIUM is the version of 5G-IANA. The 5G-IANA methodology includes an interesting test case definition approach, that was not included in the other projects. The user acceptance methodology defined in 5G-IANA, which was inspired by 5G-MOBIX, is also a good reference methodology to be used in PoDIUM. It is also important to highlight that ICT4CAR and 5G-IANA projects were coordinated by the same partner than in PoDIUM (ICCS), with a strong presence of PoDIUM partners. 5G-MOBIX also included participation of PoDIUM partners with relevant roles (ERTICO as project coordinator and ICCS as evaluation work package leader). The advantages and disadvantages of existing evaluation methodologies are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 Advantages and disadvantages of existing evaluation methodologies

Evaluation methodology	Advantages	Disadvantages
FESTA	Well-known methodology.	Designed for Field Operational Tests of mature technologies, which is not aligned with the nature of an innovation project like PoDIUM. The methodology is too complex. It requires a high learning curve. Does not include user acceptance assessment.
C-ROADS	Well-known initiative and methodology.	Focused on socio-economic impact assessment which is not the main pillar of PoDIUM’s evaluation.

<p>ICT4CART</p>	<p>Methodology applied in a CCAM project with a very similar scope to PoDIUM. Project coordinated by the same coordinator of PoDIUM and with a strong presence of PoDIUM partners.</p>	<p>The methodology does not include the definition of test cases.</p>
<p>5G-MOBIX</p>	<p>Successfully applied in an ambitious CCAM project with several trial sites. Detailed user acceptance methodology. The evaluation work package was led by PoDIUM’s project coordinator. Several PoDIUM partners participated in the project.</p>	<p>The methodology was tailored for cross-border corridor projects. Therefore, it is not directly applicable to other kind of CCAM projects like PoDIUM.</p>
<p>5G-IANA</p>	<p>The 5G-IANA evaluation work plan is organized in a very similar way to PoDIUM. Project coordinated by the same coordinator of PoDIUM and with a strong presence of PoDIUM partners.</p>	<p>The technical objectives of the project are different from PoDIUM. 5G-IANA is a 5G-PPP project that proposes a platform to deploy and run automotive network applications. Therefore, some aspects of the methodology need to be adapted to the scope of PoDIUM.</p>
<p>FAME</p>	<p>Aims to be the successor of the well-known FESTA methodology.</p>	<p>The methodology is still in draft state. The first draft was published in May 2024. By that time, PoDIUM’s evaluation methodology was already defined. The methodology includes a high number of guidelines which makes its full application very complex. The user acceptance part is not very detailed.</p>

After looking the advantages and disadvantages, it can be concluded that the technical methodologies of ICT4CART and 5G-IANA projects are the most appropriated to be adapted for PoDIUM. For user acceptance, both 5G-IANA and 5G-MOBIX projects provide interesting approaches to be taken into account. Some concrete ideas from FESTA, C-ROADS and FAME can be applied to PoDIUM, however the scope of these methodologies is different from PoDIUM.

3. PoDIUM technical evaluation methodology

3.1. Overall approach

PoDIUM’s technical evaluation methodology is mainly based on the methodologies of ICT4CART and 5G-IANA projects, enriched with the lessons learnt from previous projects where PoDIUM partners have participated. ICT4CART and 5G-IANA share with PoDIUM the same project coordinator, ICCS, and several partners, what makes the adoption of the proposed methodology easier. ICT4CART and 5G-IANA projects have also similar technological scope, organization and ambition than PoDIUM.

Even if we are not adopting the whole FESTA methodology, the three main phases of FESTA’s V model can also be used to define PoDIUM’s technical evaluation phases:

1. Preparing:
 - a. Defining the pilot: Defining functions, use cases, research questions and hypotheses
 - b. Preparing the pilot: Determining performance indicators, study design, measures and sensors, and recruiting participants
2. Using:
 - a. Conducting the pilot: Collecting data
3. Analysing:
 - a. Analysing the data: Storing and processing the data, analysing the data, answering research questions
 - b. Determining the impact: Impact assessment and deployment scenarios, socioeconomic cost–benefit analysis

In the case of PoDIUM, there is previous work done in WP2 to define the project use cases and the Key Performance Indicators (KPI). The use cases were defined in the deliverable D2.1 [10], and the KPIs in the deliverable D2.3 [7]. Use cases help validate and verify that the system or product under test, in this case the PoDIUM platform, meets the intended requirements. In PoDIUM, KPIs are derived from requirements. First, the key requirements that are critical to the success of the project were identified. Then, the metrics or performance criteria to measure the achievement of each requirement were determined. The platform requirements and specifications were defined in the deliverable D2.2 [11] and the architecture in the deliverable D3.1 [12]. KPIs influence each user’s perceived Quality of Experience (QoE), which can be assessed by collecting user feedback through surveys and interviews conducted on a statistically significant sample. This is addressed in the user acceptance evaluation methodology described in Section 6.

In the proposed technical evaluation methodology, the test cases need to be defined once the platform functions, use cases, and KPIs are defined (see Figure 1). A test case describes how to perform the test and validate that the system behaves as intended. The definition of the test cases is precisely one of the main contributions of the present deliverable D5.1.

Figure 1 Steps followed to define the PoDIUM test cases

PoDIUM’s test plan is structured in test suites. Each test suite groups several test cases related to each other. In the case of PoDIUM there are six test suites: Platform, UC1, UC2, UC3, UC4 and UC5. The test cases are the smallest unit in the hierarchy of PoDIUM’s testing approach (see Figure 2). The test cases to evaluate the platform can be found in Section 4 and the test cases to evaluate the use cases can be found in Section 5.

Figure 2 Structure of PoDIUM's test plan

Due to the scale of the demonstrations and the nature of the majority of the KPIs, some KPIs cannot be directly derived from real-time demos conducted at the various sites involved. Three alternative approaches are suggested in these cases: i) stress the network by traffic injection to obtain the maximum performance the network is able to offer; ii) Simulating real-world traffic conditions by injecting traffic into the network to mirror the expected conditions during the developed demos, including a realistic number of users, etc.; and iii) Conducting simulations (external to the network) to analyze network behaviour across various mobility and data transfer scenarios.

3.2. Reproducible and comparable experimentation

Achieving reproducible and comparable results in experimentation is crucial for the advancement of knowledge and the validation of research findings. The following actions are taken in PoDIUM to achieve this:

- **Definition of clear protocols:** the experimental protocols are defined in the test cases to minimize variability between experiments. The test cases define the experimental parameters to ensure consistency in the execution of the experiments.
- **Use of common data format:** a common data format will be used to log the evaluation data. This data format is being defined in WP4 and the definition will be included in the deliverable D4.1.
- **Performing pre-tests:** pre-tests will be conducted to assess the experimental conditions and identify potential challenges before conducting the actual experiments.
- **Documenting experimental procedures:** the PoDIUM evaluation methodology requires to document all steps of the experimental procedures, including materials used, equipment

settings, and data collection protocols. This information will be included in the deliverable D5.2. The template to report the results of each test case is defined in Section 3.4.

- **Publishing datasets:** evaluation data will be made available to other researchers to facilitate independent verification and replication of results. For this purpose, datasets will be published following the guidelines of the Data Management Plan.
- **Publishing findings in peer-reviewed scientific articles:** research findings will be submitted to peer-reviewed journals and conferences for rigorous evaluation by experts in the field. Peer review helps identify potential issues with experimental design, analysis, or interpretation.

3.3. Test case template

The PoDIUM test case template is based on the one used in the 5G-IANA project [13], with some minor modifications done inspired on the conformance testing defined in 3GPP TS 38.523-1 V17.6.0 [8].

Table 2 Test case template

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_XXX
Context / Use Case	Platform or Use Case (include use case number)
KPI	Reference one KPI identifier defined in D2.3 that will be used to assess the result of the test.
Test purpose	Describe the objective of the test.
Pre-test conditions	List any setup or preconditions necessary to execute the test successfully. This might include initializing the system, configuring settings, or establishing specific starting conditions.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Describe the expected outcomes or results. This could include expected behaviours, outputs, responses, or system states.
Test procedure sequence	List the steps or actions required to execute the test case. Provide clear instructions for carrying out the test, including any interactions with the system or inputs provided.
Verification criteria	Specify the criteria used to verify the correctness or success of the test. This must include comparing actual outcome against expected result. For example: If the result is higher than the KPI target value: PASS If the result is lower than the KPI target value: FAIL Instead of a pass/fail criteria, a grading system can be used. For instance, qualifying the performance of the system under test as “good”, “average”, or “low”.

3.4. Documentation and reporting

The documentation serves dual purposes: it acts as a reference for future testing and provides a comprehensive record of the testing process. Once the evaluation data have been gathered, they will undergo thorough analysis using statistical methods. The findings will be illustrated through graphical plots to enhance understanding and clarity. The primary objective of this analysis is to uncover patterns, trends, and outliers based on the pre-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These results will be evaluated against the target values specified for each KPI. By doing so, we can assess the overall performance and identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential areas for improvement. To achieve this, the results will be benchmarked against established standards or industry norms where available. This comparison will help in pinpointing specific areas that require attention and highlight aspects that meet or exceed expectations.

Following this detailed analysis, conclusions will be drawn regarding the performance and effectiveness of the PoDIUM platform and the solutions developed for the various use cases. These conclusions will provide insights into how well the platform is functioning and where it excels or falls short. Furthermore, based on the insights gained, we will formulate recommendations for the effective deployment of PoDIUM technologies. These recommendations will address any identified issues and propose actionable solutions to ensure the successful implementation and optimization of the platform in real-world scenarios. This comprehensive approach aims to enhance the overall effectiveness and efficiency of PoDIUM technologies, ensuring they meet the intended goals and deliver value in their respective use cases.

The results and conclusions of each test case will be documented following the same table template (Table 3), which is based on the one used in 5G-MOBIX's deliverable D5.2 "Report on technical evaluation" [4]. A preliminary version of this table was included in the deliverable D2.3. This table shows the evaluation results using descriptive statistics and a graphical representation (plot). The descriptive statistics include the total number of samples used for obtaining the results, the mean, the median, the standard deviation, the maximum and minimum values, the confidence interval (CI) at the 95% level and the percentile 95. The plot type will be selected depending on the KPI, but the following ones will be considered: box plots, scatter plots, histograms and Cumulative distribution function (CDF) plots. A KPI is a scalar value providing information on system under-test performance or scenario quality. KPIs can be divided into continuous (metrics) and binary values (pass/fail criteria). In the cases where the KPI has a binary pass/fail criteria, the percentage of times that the KPI criteria have been fulfilled will be used as the evaluation metric and the same statistics described in Table 3 will apply.

Table 3 Template for the presentation of the technical evaluation results

Test case identifier				
Materials used	<i>Include specification and/or settings of the equipment used</i>			
KPI				
Descriptive Statistics	# total samples	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
	Max	Min	CI 95%	Percentile 95
Plot	<i>Include the most representative plot option for the KPI: box plot, scatter plot, histograms or Cumulative distribution function (CDF).</i>			
Conclusions	<i>Discuss the results considering the test verification criteria defined in the test case.</i>			

4. PoDIUM platform evaluation

The PoDIUM platform will be evaluated with seven test cases, that cover KPIs from five categories according to 5G-PPP's second white paper about KPIs [14]:

- **Service availability:** KPI_P_1_serviceAvailability
- **Latency:** KPI_P_2-updateLatency, KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
- **Compute:** KPI_P_4-processingDelay, KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime, KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
- **Service reliability:** KPI_P_5-comReliability
- **Security:** KPI_P_6-SealedObject

Therefore, the PoDIUM platform test cases aim to assess the performance and completeness of the platform. The specific applicability of the platform is assessed with the use case tests, that are described in Section 5. The quality of experience of the users is evaluated with the user acceptance evaluation described in Section 6.

Table 4 Test case TC_KPI_P_1_serviceAvailability

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_1_serviceAvailability
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_1_serviceAvailability
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate service availability.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Logs should contain a line every 10 seconds of the service working.
Test procedure sequence	<p>When other tests or demos are running, every service involved should emit logs while running. Logs are obtained and stored at the end of the test.</p> <p>The logs should be processed to obtain the amount of outage time, accumulating the time slots reported in the log and the time of the missing slots or time of unacceptable outage.</p>
Verification criteria	<p>The result availability percentage for service i would be $R_i = 1 - (\text{totalTime} / \text{outageTime})$.</p> <p>If the mean R for all services is equal or higher than the KPI target value : PASS</p> <p>If the mean R for all services is lower than the KPI target value: FAIL</p>

Table 5 Test case TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_2-updateLatency
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_2-updateLatency
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate update latency of the platform
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during other tests executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.

Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries, one that identifies the detection of the event (possibly with the timestamp of detection in the past) and another log entry that declares its input into the DT. The first log entry is taken in the nearest point of detection; the second is in the nearest point of consumption in DT.
Test procedure sequence	When other tests or demos are running, the sensor software logs every single detection event with its the detection time; correspondingly the DT interface in input will log the detection input. Logs are collected; the detection and digital twin input messages should be correlated in the logs, perhaps by a join field to process both logs together.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (DT timestamp – detection timestamp) and obtain the 95 percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value : PASS If the 95% percentile remains after the KPI target value: FAIL

Table 6 Test case TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
Test purpose	Obtain measurements to calculate the latency of the platform to notify a road user regarding a road event.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during use case executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are going.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries, one that identifies the end of the computation of a notification message (DENM, IVIM, GPM) and another log entry that records its reception in the road user (CAV or VRU). The first log entry is taken in the nearest point of computation; the second is in the nearest point of consumption in the road user.
Test procedure sequence	The output of the final C-ITS application must be logged and also the CAV / VRU OBUs. Both log entries should be identified and then their timestamps are used to calculate the time deltas for every notification produced.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (Road User timestamp – notification generation timestamp) and obtain the 95 percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value : PASS If the 95% percentile remains after the KPI target value: FAIL

Table 7 Test case TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_4-processingDelay
Context / Use Case	Platform

KPI	KPI_P_4-processingDelay
Test purpose	Obtain the measurements to calculate the latency of the platform to generate a notification as a result of a road event.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during use case executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are running.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Two log entries are required in the final C-ITS application in MEC or cloud. Ideally the second and first log entries of TC_KPI_P_2 and 3 respectively are enough, since they contain the timestamps that determine time passed between the detection of an event and the corresponding notification generated. Both messages are required to be linked by a join field that correlates the event with its notification and so both logs are joint together.
Test procedure sequence	The output of the final C-ITS application must be logged and also the CAV / VRU OBUs. Both log entries should be identified and then their timestamps are used to calculate the time deltas for every notification produced.
Verification criteria	The calculation of the CDF of the all the time deltas (Road User timestamp – notification generation timestamp) and obtain the 95 percentile. If the 95% percentile remains within KPI target value: PASS If the 95% percentile remains after the KPI target value: FAIL

Table 8 Test case TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_5-comReliability
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_5-comReliability
Test purpose	Obtain the measurements to estimate how much reliable is the platform relaying messages between interfaces
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during use case executions, when demonstrations or other KPI tests are running.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	For the most critical interfaces in the system, a logging should be performed at both sides of the interface. Both messages are required to be linked by a join field that correlates the outgoing and incoming message in the interface.
Test procedure sequence	All messages matched in both logs are counted and all messages not matched at all are counted too. This is done for every use case run.
Verification criteria	The ratio between not matched and total messages is calculated If the 95% percentile of all UC runs remains within KPI target value : PASS If the 95% percentile of all UC runs remains after the KPI target value: FAIL

Table 9 Test case TC_KPI_P_6-SealedObject

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_6-SealedObject
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_6-SealedObject
Test purpose	This test measures the capability of the platform to protect sensible data/objects through the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and its sealing/unsealing features.
Pre-test conditions	Having defined a trusted status and one or more sensitive files to be unsealed.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	For each test an entry defines the status of the system during that test (trusted or untrusted) and the result of unsealing (success or failure)
Test procedure sequence	For each test, the status of the system (trusted or untrusted) is logged, and a protected file is unsealed. If this operation is successful, 'success' is logged, otherwise 'failure'. The test is repeated several times with different system status.
Verification criteria	<p>It must be possible to unseal with success only in trusted state so the unsealing success rate for trusted status would be</p> $R_{unsealing_trusted_state} = 1 - (failTrust / numTrust) * 100$ <p>and for untrusted status would be</p> $R_{unsealing_untrusted_state} = 1 - (succUntrust / numUntrust) * 100$ <p>numTrust = number of tests with trusted system failTrust = number of failures in tests with trusted system succUntrust = number of successes in tests with untrusted system numUntrust = number of tests with untrusted system</p> <p>If both $R_{unsealing_trusted_state}$ and $R_{unsealing_untrusted_state}$ are equal or higher than the KPI target value: PASS otherwise FAIL;</p>

Table 10 Test case TC_KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime
Test purpose	Measurements taken to evaluate the additional bootstrap time due to the Software Integrity Architecture.
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done starting with the platform switched off
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The boot time of the platform
Test procedure sequence	Starting with the platform switched off, the timer is started at the same time as the platform is switched on (e.g. by pressing the power

	button) and is stopped when the OS login screen is reached. The test is performed with and without Software Integrity Architecture.
Verification criteria	<p>The result percentage would be $R = ((\text{bootTime_with_SIA} - \text{bootTime_without_SIA}) / \text{bootTime_without_SIA}) * 100$</p> <p>bootTime_with_SIA = the bootstrap time of the platform with the Software Integrity Architecture.</p> <p>bootTime_without_SIA = the bootstrap time of the platform the without Software Integrity Architecture.</p> <p>If R is equal or lower than the KPI target value: PASS, otherwise FAIL;</p>

Table 11 Test case TC_KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
Context / Use Case	Platform
KPI	KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
Test purpose	Measurements taken to evaluate the additional CPU utilization and memory consumption due to the Software Integrity Architecture
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during normal operation of the device
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Logs of the CPU load in % and memory consumption in Byte or multiples
Test procedure sequence	The platform runs its common applications/services while logging the CPU load in % and memory consumption. The test is performed with and without Software Integrity Architecture.
Verification criteria	<p>The result percentage for the CPU load would be R_CPU and for the memory consumption would be $R_mem = ((\text{mem_with_SIA} - \text{mem_without_SIA}) / \text{mem_without_SIA}) * 100$</p> <p>mem_with_SIA = the memory consumption of the platform with the Software Integrity Architecture.</p> <p>mem_without_SIA = the memory consumption of the platform without the Software Integrity Architecture.</p> <p>If both R_CPU and R_mem are equal or lower than their KPI target value: PASS, otherwise FAIL;</p>

Table 12 Test case TC_KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation
Context / Use Case	Running the Remote Attestation protocol.
KPI	KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation
Test purpose	Measurements taken to calculate the performance of the Remote Attestation protocol
Pre-test conditions	The test should be done during normal operation of the device
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Log entries with the duration of the Remote Attestation measured on the Verifier side
Test procedure sequence	The attestation software measures the duration in seconds from the beginning of the Remote Attestation protocol to its end. The test is repeated several times to reach statistical relevance
Verification criteria	If the mean duration R is equal or lower than the KPI target value: PASS, otherwise FAIL;

5. Use cases evaluation

The PoDIUM use cases are complimentary and test the PoDIUM platform capabilities from different angles and in different driving scenarios (urban, highway and even in a cross-border corridor). The use cases evaluation complements the agnostic platform tests to prove that the PoDIUM architecture is able to accommodate heterogeneous functions to enable a wide range of CCAM use cases.

5.1. UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

The UC1 will be evaluated in an urban scenario with two test cases that evaluate if a CAV using the PoDIUM functions is able to successfully pass a lane blockage while another CAV or connected VRU approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.

Table 13 Test case TC_KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Maneuver-CAV

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Maneuver-CAV
Context / Use Case	UC1 Scenario 1
KPI	KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Maneuver-CAV
Test purpose	Test if the CAV is able to successfully pass a blockage while another CAV approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Pre-test conditions	<p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of autonomous driving trials.</p> <p>The traffic is flowing normally on both lanes.</p> <p>All PoDIUM functions run normally.</p> <p>Then, a lane blockage is detected and a CAV needs to pass this blockage while another CAV approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The CAVs have successfully passed the blockage. An expert or a group of experts mark the test run as either successful or not.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled 2. The two CAV approach the blockage in such a way that the cooperative planner initiates a cooperative manoeuvre 3. The two CAV pass the blockage according to the received manoeuvre 4. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. <p>Repeat the test at least five times.</p> <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>Divide the number of successful test runs by the number of total test runs.</p> <p>If the result is higher than 75%: PASS</p> <p>If the result is not higher than 75%: FAIL</p>

Table 14 Test case TC_KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Maneuver-VRU

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Maneuver-VRU
Context / Use Case	UC1 Scenario 2
KPI	KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Maneuver-VRU
Test purpose	Test if the CAV is able to successfully pass a blockage while a connected VRU approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.
Pre-test conditions	<p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of autonomous driving trials.</p> <p>The traffic is flowing normally on both lanes.</p> <p>All PoDIUM functions run normally.</p> <p>Then, a lane blockage is detected and a CAV needs to pass this blockage while a connected VRU approaches the blockage on the non-blocked lane.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	The VRU on the free lane has passed the obstacle without getting into a dangerous situation. Additionally, the CAV on the blocked lane has passed the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre. An expert or a group of experts mark the test run as either successful or not.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled 2. The CAV and VRU approach the blockage in such a way that the cooperative planner initiates a cooperative manoeuvre 3. The two CAV pass the blockage according to the received manoeuvre 4. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. <p>Repeat the test at least five times.</p> <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>Divide the number of successful test runs by the number of total test runs.</p> <p>If the result is higher than 75%: PASS</p> <p>If the result is not higher than 75%: FAIL</p>

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Maneuver-MultiC
Context / Use Case	UC1 Scenario 1
KPI	KPI_UC1_3-Cooperative-Maneuver-MultiC
Test purpose	Test if Multi-Connectivity is able to utilize all available communication technologies successfully at the same time.
Pre-test conditions	<p>CAV, RSU and MEC all support multi-connectivity using the Scheduler module.</p> <p>All PoDIUM functions run normally.</p> <p>The CAV is in coverage of 5G-cmWave, 5G-mmWave and 60GHz adhoc.</p>

Expected result (conformance requirements)	Data is transmitted by the CAV successfully over all available communication technologies successfully at the same time and successfully reaches the MEC.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that all pre-test conditions are fulfilled 2. The CAV initiates transmission to the MEC 3. The sending scheduler passes the data to the different communication technologies and the receiving scheduler processes the incoming streams. 4. The expert or a group of experts compare the test run against the expected result. <p>Repeat the test at least 50 times.</p>
Verification criteria	<p>Divide the number of successful test-runs by the number of total test-runs.</p> <p>If the result is higher than 95%: PASS</p> <p>If the result is not higher than 95%: FAIL</p>

5.2. UC2: PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

The UC2 will be evaluated with seven test cases, that evaluate how the PoDIUM infrastructure and software improves different aspects of the traffic management such as the efficient management of traffic lights to prioritize emergency vehicles, and the correct calculation of Origin-Destination (O-D) matrices and travel time and delay per road segment. In addition, in UC2, the quality of experience and safety improvements of the drivers or passengers of CV/CAVs will be evaluated by measuring percentage of times for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV and the average reduction of the response time by CV/CAVs when there is high risk of collision with a VRU.

Table 15 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement
Context / Use Case	UC2 Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor
KPI	KPI_UC2_Traffic_light_flow_improvement
Test purpose	Measure the improvement in the percentage of times that EVs find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection cause by the improvement of EV priority management applied within UC2.
Pre-test conditions	<p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.</p> <p>EV with the PODIUM equipment and software installed.</p> <p>PODIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation).</p> <p>Data model of the emergency corridor provided.</p>

<p>Expected result (conformance requirements)</p>	<p>The EV finds green at its arrival to intersections and crossed them without stopping nor significantly reduce its speed.</p>
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<p>With the PODIUM service enabled:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The EV initiates a trip along the corridor and notifies the PODIUM enhanced priority management service 2. The EV sends CAM messages to the PODIUM platform informing about its position and speed 3. The EV priority management service estimates the arrival time at each intersection, using the position received from the EV to improve the estimation 4. The EV priority management activates priority for the EV at the traffic controllers with a reasonable anticipation to the estimated arrival of the EV to the intersection 5. The EV arrives at and crosses each intersection 6. Logs are collected to check the time and speed of the EV when arriving to the intersection. If available, the state of traffic lights at each time obtained from the local controller will be also collected. 7. The percentage of trips in which the EV crossed the intersection without stopping or reducing speed significantly and (if available) with green light is calculated <p>Baseline</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The EV initiates a trip along the corridor and notifies the legacy priority management service 2. The EV sends CAM messages to the PODIUM platform informing about its position and speed 3. Several beacons installed along the corridor are activated while the vehicle passes besides them 4. The EV priority management system estimates arrival time at intersections using only the beacon activation and a pre-configured speed profile. CAM messages are ignored. 5. The EV priority management activates priority for the EV at the traffic controllers 6. The EV arrives at and crosses each intersection 7. Logs are collected to check the time and speed of the EV when arriving to the intersection. If available, the state of traffic lights at each time obtained from the local controller will be also collected. 8. The percentage of trips in which the EV crossed the intersection without stopping or reducing speed significantly and/or (if available) with green light is calculated <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>

Verification criteria	<p>The increase of the percentage of trips in which the EV finds green (and/or crosses without stopping nor reducing speed) with regards to the percentage measured for baseline tests:</p> <p>>10% .- Very good</p> <p>>5% - Good:</p> <p>0-2 % - Fair</p> <p><0 -Bad:</p>
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Table 16 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD
Context / Use Case	UC2 Traffic optimisation // Calculation of O-D matrices
KPI	KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD
Test purpose	Calculate the percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS when generating O-D matrix data
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. O-D zones modelled CVs with the PODIUM equipment and software installed. PODIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation).
Expected result (conformance requirements)	O-D matrix data are generated per time period, consistent with the trips made by connected vehicles.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connected vehicles conduct as many trips as possible, during the test period and across the pilot demonstration area, from different origins and destinations 2. The CV send CAM messages to the PODIUM platform informing about their position and speed 3. The PODIUM service for traffic metrics generation receives the information, detects the beginning and end of each trip, stores the anonymises the data, aggregates them per time period and generates an O-D matrix per period 4. Logs are collected to check the time and location of the beginning and end of each trip. They are processed and compared with the generated O-D to check consistency <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	Percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS. Success: >95%

Table 17 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay
Context / Use Case	UC2 Traffic optimisation // Calculation of travel time and delay per road segment
KPI	KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay
Test purpose	Calculate the percentage of travel times across road links correctly processed
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. City data model available CVs with the PODIUM equipment and software installed. PODIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation).
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Average travel time and delay per road junction data are generated per time period, consistent with the trips made by connected vehicles.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connected vehicles conduct as many trips as possible, during the test period and across the pilot demonstration area, from different origins and destinations 2. The CV send CAM messages to the PODIUM platform informing about their position and speed 3. The PODIUM service for traffic metrics generation receives the information, tracks their movement along road segments, calculates the travel tie and delay, stores the anonymises the data, aggregates them per time period and generates metrics per time period (average travel time, average speed, average and accumulated delay) 4. Logs are collected to check the time and location of the beginning and end of each trip. They are processed and compared with the generated travel time to check consistency
Verification criteria	Percentage of trips along road segments for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS. Success: >95%

Table 18 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction
Context / Use Case	UC2 Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor
KPI	KPI_UC2_4-EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction
Test purpose	Measure the reduction of the extra red traffic light times for movements transversal to the EV corridor caused by guard times of the management of priority for EV

<p>Pre-test conditions</p>	<p>At least fair results of KPI_UC2_1 should have been previously obtained with long guard times. Guard times configuration reduced</p>
<p>Expected result (conformance requirements)</p>	<p>By improving the accuracy of the estimation of the arrival time of EV at intersections, it is expected that less guard time will be required and crossing vehicles and pedestrians will have to stop less time at read lights.</p>
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<p>Repetition of the same tests described for TC_KPI_UC2_1, but with configuring progressively reduced guard times, until the KP_UC2_1 becomes affected. This iteration process should be done for both the baseline and with the PODIUM service enabled. For each repetition, it is necessary to calculate the duration of the priority for EV activation interval at each intersection, subtract the standard travel time for the EV at the entering road segment (length / standard speed), multiplied by the proportion of green time per cycle for transversal roads in a reference traffic plan. Calculate the average of this value for, on one side, the baseline tests, and for the tests with the PODIUM service enabled.</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>Calculate the percentage of reduction. ≥25 % Success <25 % Fail</p>

Table 19 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_5-EV_successful_coop_manoeuvres_percentage

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_5-EV_successful_coop_manoeuvres_percentage
Context / Use Case	UC2 Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor
KPI	KPI_UC2_5-EV_percentage_sucesful_coop_manoeuvre
Test purpose	Calculation of the percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV.
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. City data model available CAVs/CVs with the PODIUM equipment and software installed. PODIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation). Data model of the emergency corridor provided. EV with the PODIUM equipment and software installed. The planned routes of CAVs/CVs for the demo should include some common road segments with pre-defined EV corridors, and be timed to facilitate the coincidence of EVs and CAVs/CVs in some of the road segments
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an EV moves has to overtake an CAV or CV at a road segment, the PODIUM service sends a DENM warning message, that is correctly displayed to the driver (for CVs) or causes the CAV to execute a manoeuvre to facilitate the EV passing.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CV/CVs start their trips across the demo area 2. EV starts its trip along one emergency corridor 3. Coincidence of EV and some CAVs/CVs in the same road segment at the same time occurs during the trip, having the EV to overtake the CAV /CV 4. Before such coincidence happens the PODIUM should have sent a DENM message to the CAVs/CVs of interest 5. CAV should execute a cooperative manoeuvre autonomously 6. A warning should be displayed in HMI of CV, requesting the driver to execute a cooperative manoeuvre 7. Analysis of logs from the EV, the CAV/CVs and the service. Detection of the events of coincidence of an EV and a CAV or CV at the same road segment. 8. Observation of the HMI of CV or CAV (check when warnings are display) 9. Observation of the response by CAV to the reception of the warning <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	Percentage of coincidences for which a cooperative manoeuvre is correctly displayed at HMI or executed by CAV: >=95 % Success <95 % Fail

Table 20 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_6-VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_6-VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction
Context / Use Case	UC2 VRU protection
KPI	KPI_UC2_6_VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction
Test purpose	Calculate the average reduction of the response time by CV/CAVs when there is high risk of collision with a VRU
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. CAVs/CVs with the PODIUM equipment and software installed (OBU) PODIUM equipment installed in the intersection, including an RSU and an Edge computer with PODIUM software installed (including the Collision Risk estimation functionality) Cameras with AI functionality for VRU detection installed at the intersection pointing to the potential collision risk areas between vehicles and VRUs
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an event of high risk of collision between a CAV or CV and a VRU is predicted, a DENM messages is received by the vehicle, and the vehicle reduces its speed a significant time interval before the arrival to the potential collision location
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CAV/CVs moves towards the intersection at a speed near the maximum permitted 2. The CAV/CV sends CAM message periodically, informing about is position and speed 3. A VRU approaches the intersection in a potentially dangerous situation (lack of visibility, red light) 4. The AI cameras detect the VRU and the CRE detects a situation of high risk of collision 5. The CRE sends a DENM message to the vehicles approaching he intersection 6. The CAV reduces speed automatically when receiving the message. A warning is displayed in the HMI of the CV and the driver reduces the speed 7. Calculate the time from the detection to the reaction, by comparing the timestamps in the logs of the CRE and the logs in the CV and CAVs (or observing the HMI display) 8. Repeat the test multiple times and calculate the average <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	Success: reduction >20% with regards to an estimated reaction time for the baseline case

Table 21 Test case TC_KPI_UC2_7-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC2_7-Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration
Context / Use Case	UC2 VRU protection
KPI	KPI_UC2_7_Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration
Test purpose	Calculate the reduction of the proportion of events of high risk of collision with a VRU for which the CV/CAVs has to make a hard braking
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. CAVs/CVs with the PODIUM equipment and software installed (OBU) PODIUM equipment installed in the intersection, including an RSU and an Edge computer with PODIUM software installed (including the Collision Risk estimation functionality) Cameras with AI functionality for VRU detection installed at the intersection pointing to the potential collision risk areas between vehicles and VRUs
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Each time an event of high risk of collision between a CAV or CV and a VRU is predicted, a DENM messages is received by the vehicle, and the vehicle reduces its speed in advance, enough seconds before the vehicle sensors detecting the VRU, so when the detection happens the vehicle does not need to make a hard braking
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CAV/CVs moves towards the intersection at a speed near the maximum permitted 2. The CAV/CV sends CAM message periodically, informing about is position and speed 3. A VRU approaches the intersection in a potentially dangerous situation (lack of visibility, red light) 4. The AI cameras detect the VRU and the CRE detects a situation of high risk of collision 5. The CRE sends a DENM message to the vehicles approaching he intersection 6. The CAV reduces speed automatically when receiving the message. A warning is displayed in the HMI of the CV and the driver reduces the speed 7. Collect the logs from CRE and the logs from the CV (to identify the high risk of collision events) and the logs from CAVs/CVs (looking for speeds and acceleration) 8. Repeat the test multiple times and calculate proportion of cases in which a hard braking (high deceleration) is registered in the logs of the vehicle (directly or by dividing speed reduction by time) <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	Calculate the percentage of risk of collision detections for which the reaction of the CV or CAV to avoid the collision implied a hard braking. Compare with the estimated estimation proportion for the baseline case Success : reduction >20%

5.3. UC3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

The evaluation of UC3 is designed for a cross-border corridor context. Therefore, the most relevant issue in this context, the service interruption time while switching from one country 5G network to the other, is going to be addressed. Cross-border corridors are non-urban roads where vehicles can usually drive at high speed. Due to this, the capability of the CAV shuttle to achieve 80 km/h is also going to be assessed, as well as the capability to reduce the maximum speed using the implemented traffic strategy. The service delivery time is also going to be measured.

Table 22 Test case TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime
Context / Use Case	Use case 3
KPI	KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime
Test purpose	Measure the Service delivery time (i.e. the reaction time at service layer) from time of incident detection or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, until incident notification of CVs and updated traffic instructions (“manoeuvres”) received by CVs.
Pre-test conditions	<p>A. Virtual simulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MEC deployed, operational and connected to internet. (incl. TMC, GW, LDM modules). - OBU-stack deployed in lab settings and connected to MEC. <p>B. Validation of the KPI in real conditions on the highway (additional to the above)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OBU hardware and OBU-stack set up in vehicles (e.g. IDIADA). - The CVs are moving along the highway. - Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>The Platform must be able to detect incidents, or other changes in traffic, and generate and dispatch the respective CCAM messages (alerts, traffic strategies) which must be received by the CVs via 5G and/or C-V2X within a targeted timeframe.</p> <p>This KPI detects the “pace” of operation within the context of UC3. This time includes communication time, but also internal processing times:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incident alert relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives an incident notification. Target value: < 2s 2. Strategy relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection (or other strategy update trigger) until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives the updated TMC traffic strategy (manoeuvre instruction). Target value: < 6s
Test procedure sequence	<p>Measurement of durations will be calculated, by taking as:</p> <p>Starting time: the time of incident detection (as measured by the event timestamp within the MEC), or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, and</p> <p>End times or milestone times:</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incident alert: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). 2. Strategy relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). <p>Multiple measurements (> 10) will take place in virtual simulation (false triggers in pre-demonstration technical trials), where max target values must be achieved every time. Some measurements in real road will take place both through 5G and C-V2X communication channels, to account for latency.</p>
Verification criteria	<p>PASS: if #2 time is <2s and #4 time is < 6s after incident detection by the MEC in at least 80% of the measurements in virtual simulation and in real road</p> <p>FAIL: if #2 time is >2s and #4 time >6s in more than 20% of the cases.</p>

Table 23 Test case TC_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime
Context / Use Case	Use case 3
KPI	KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime
Test purpose	<p>Measure the Cross border interruption time (i.e. avoid interruption of service while switching from one country 5G network to the other)</p> <p>While crossing the France-Spain border, ensure that the 5G connection interruption is minimal, and be complemented via C-V2X coverage and will not cause any significant service interruption.</p>
Pre-test conditions	<p>The platform is operational. The CV / CAV is equipped with OBU and able to connect to 5G/C-V2X. The RSUs are installed on the highway, operational and connected to the MEC. Two 5G networks are available, one for each side of the border.</p> <p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Seamless connectivity via C-V2X when 5G network service is interrupted on the border section of the highway.
Test procedure sequence	<p>The CV (or CAV) initiates its journey from one side of the border (e.g. in France).</p> <p>The CV crosses over the border and continues its journey (e.g. in Spain). 5G service is briefly interrupted due to change of network operator. Meanwhile, the CV connects via C-V2X to the platform. The time of interruption and reconnection is logged (based on the packages received in the Gateway by a certain vehicle, as well in the vehicles' OBUs).</p> <p>Note: If it is not possible to experience the real interruption in the border segment, we recreate an equivalent duration (e.g. 5 seconds) interruption of 5G service in another area covered by C-V2X RSUs.</p> <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>PASS: If the connection of the CV to the MEC is interrupted for < 500ms</p> <p>FAIL: If the connection of the CV to the MEC is interrupted for > 500ms</p>

	Multiple measurements (at least 5) will take place. The result must be PASS in at least 3/5.
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Table 24 Test case TC_KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed
Context / Use Case	Use case 3
KPI	KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed
Test purpose	MILLA's CAV Shuttle needs to be capable to achieve 80km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.
Pre-test conditions	<p>This will be validated in a closed circuit in France. Demonstrated on the LL highway in Spain.</p> <p>For the highway demo: CAV is fully operational in SAE4 (pre-approved). Highway permits for CAV circulation obtained. The MILLA shuttle is at the origin point of the route, ready to go. Safety driver is in the Shuttle. Safety car(s) is below the shuttle, following along the way.</p> <p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	MILLA Shuttle successfully and safely navigating at 80km/h in SAE4 on the highway.
Test procedure sequence	<p>The MILLA shuttle initiates at the origin point of the route, working in AD mode. When allowed by legal speed limits, it accelerates to 80km/h automatically. It arrives to the point of destination.</p> <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>PASS: If it reaches 80km/h in SAE4</p> <p>FAIL: If it is less than 70km/h</p>

Table 25 Test case TC_KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation

Test Case ID	KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation
Context / Use Case	Use case 3
KPI	KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation
Test purpose	<p>Evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by the CAV (autonomously) and the CV drivers (manually).</p> <p>For practical reasons we will only focus on the following traffic strategy that is transmitted to the vehicles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce max speed to X km/h (speed limit to be defined depending on traffic conditions, below 120 km/h)
Pre-test conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. There are in total 4 vehicle available, with their respective drivers. Drivers have been briefed about the experiment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CVs and CAV fully equipped with OBUs and HMIs (tablets/laptops), and connected to internet and C-V2X. • Platform fully operational and connected (MEC), capable of emitting traffic strategies to the vehicles.
<p>Expected result (conformance requirements)</p>	<p>Traffic strategies are successfully implemented by the automated vehicles (CAV) and the connected vehicle drivers (CV), within a reasonable time frame of reaction. Target value, from the moment of reception of the strategy by the vehicles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay of CAVs applying indicated strategy < 5s. • Delay of CV drivers applying indicated strategy < 10s
<p>Test procedure sequence</p>	<p>CVs and CAV circulating on the highway with the respective drivers.</p> <p>The vehicles receive CCAM messages to reduce their speed, as prescribed by the new speed limit announced by the Platform.</p> <p>The vehicles react to the new traffic strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CAV reduces speed automatically, without driver intervention. • The CV drivers read the message on their in-vehicle HMI screens and slow down their vehicles accordingly. <p>Data loggers capture the “start and end of manoeuvre”.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start of manoeuvre: Timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and displayed in the HMI • End of manoeuvre: Timestamp of the Logged speeds of the vehicles (CVs & CAV) as stored in the MEC, when vehicle speed is first-time equal to the new speed limit. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>For each strategy we will trial 3x times the manoeuvre with all 4 vehicles (CV and CAV) and calculate the time of reaction of the vehicles. In total 12 samples of strategy implementation manoeuvres.</p> <p>PASS: If the strategies are implemented and the manoeuvre (speed reduction) is completed within the targeted reaction times, in at least 2/3 of the trial cases (to account for human error), while the other cases not having a very significant deviation or grave issue of implementation (e.g. messages not received, delays in transmission)</p> <p>FAIL: If >1/3 of the trials (5 or more out of 12) exceed the targeted reaction times.</p>

5.4. UC4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

In the UC4 the performance of the implemented CCAM functions to improve intersection manoeuvring will be evaluated. This includes measuring the performance of VRU detection by the PoDIUM system in terms of true positives/negatives, measuring the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the scenarios, evaluating the Podium VIMA application (managing precedence at crossroads) in terms of impact on crossing manoeuvres and testing if the end-to-end reaction time from hazard detection at RSU until actuation/warning at CAV is enough.

Table 26 Test case TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance
Context / Use Case	UC4 Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance
KPI	KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance
Test purpose	Measure the performance of VRU detection by the Podium system, in terms of true positives/negatives.
Pre-test conditions	CAV, PODIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational. Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads. Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	CAV performs the following scenarios, with expected results 1.1 Straight pass – expected negative (no warning: VRU is still) 1.2 Straight warn – expected positive (warning: VRU violates red) 2.1 Right Turn with precedence management –expected positive (information: VRU is going to cross first) 2.2 Right Turn with sudden crossing – expected positive (warning: imminent VRU crossing) 3.1 Left turn - expected positive (information: VRU and other cars’ are going to cross first) Trials are repeated for each scenario with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPM only (infrastructure detections then processed by CAV to give indications) • DENM/IVIM only (infrastructure-based warnings/indications) • CPM+DENM/IVIM (combination of the former strategies) The expectation is that the three methods give slightly different results and that the last one (combination) sums the benefits of the former ones.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run scenario in a controlled way for CAV and VRU (but in open traffic) according to the step-by-step description, with Podium system activated. 2. Check and annotate the HMI warnings on CAV. In parallel collect data logs.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Classify the true/false positive/negatives from annotation - note: this step helps spotting and isolating the most evident faults). 4. Verify the true/false positive/negatives from data logs - note: this step thoroughly checks and helps spotting any other faults, maybe not evident by HMI (e.g. stray warnings, or inaccurate warnings not noticed live during the trials) 5. Calculate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PI1: true positive rate (probability of detection): true positives over total expected positives • PI2: true negative rate (1-false positive rate) is the number of true negative over total expected negatives <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	If the applicable PI (depending on the expected positive/negative) in each scenario are >90%, the system has reached its goals at this prototype verification stage (NOTE: product validation requires higher percentages)

Table 27 Test case TC_KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban
Context / Use Case	UC4 Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance
KPI	KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban
Test purpose	Measure the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the scenarios
Pre-test conditions	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials. CAV operational in UC4 scenarios. PODIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational. Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	CAV is capable of self-localizing in-lane and lane-level accuracy is expected in most of the tests. The addition of RTK is expected to yield sub-meter accuracy. Outliers should be mainly due to poor GNSS signals. The latter cases may degrade or even compromise scenario functionality.
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record positioning data (including confidence ellipse and number of satellites in view), along with the Use Case functionality data (e.g. manoeuvre, HMI, etc.). 2. Compute average positioning accuracy during scenario trials, Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle over the entire duration of each trial. 3. In post-processing, compare positioning accuracy results with use case functionality and performance.

	Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).
Verification criteria	<p>< 0.2m 95% of the time with RTK correction is passed</p> <p>< 1.5m 95% of the time without RTK correction is passed</p> <p>The percentage is calculated over the sampled position data in time span of each trial.</p> <p>Outlier cases (not passed) should be analysed against use case functionality and performance in those specific conditions (along with context information, such as number of satellites, etc.).</p>

Table 28 Test case TC_KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvr_optimization

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvr_optimization
Context / Use Case	<p>UC4</p> <p>Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvr Assistance</p>
KPI	KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvr_optimization
Test purpose	Evaluate Podium VIMA application (managing precedence at crossroads) in terms of impact on crossing manoeuvres.
Pre-test conditions	<p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.</p> <p>CAV operational in UC4 scenarios.</p> <p>PODIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational.</p> <p>Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	<p>With respect to a non-assisted crossing, the expectation is that the VIMA-assisted crossing yields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • similar waiting times for CAV to cross: not much higher, not much lower • anticipated reactions, in terms of time/space when vehicle starts braking/accelerating. • smoother speed profile during the whole crossing
Test procedure sequence	<p>The KPI is applicable to the following test scenarios</p> <p>2.1 Right Turn with precedence management</p> <p>3.1 Left turn</p> <p>Trials here are divided in baseline and treatment</p> <p>[ref. FESTA Handbook V8, September 2021, V8, https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/FESTA-Handbook-Version-8.pdf].</p> <p>Baseline: VRU crossing trial with system on, and no HMI.</p> <p>Treatment: VRU crossing trial with Podium system active and HMI with driving recommendation (as CAV automated control is not foreseen in UC4).</p> <p>Since Podium system records a lot of data during the use case, it is advised, even in the baseline, to run Podium system “as is” in background, in order</p>

	<p>to record the scene. This is useful for checking vehicle and VRU crossing, as well as context information (e.g. traffic) and for making sure that the treatment recordings were done in similar conditions as the baseline ones.</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the test and record manoeuvre data 2. Analyse data comparing treatment and baseline, addressing in particular: manoeuvre start time (vehicle starts decelerating), maximum acceleration/deceleration values, manoeuvre timing <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
Verification criteria	<p>Positive impact on manoeuvre is evaluated if results yield</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <+/-20% deviation in total time to cross > 10% reaction time advance (treatment/baseline) > 10% reduction in maximum acceleration/deceleration values

Table 29 Test case TC_KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing
Context / Use Case	<p>UC4</p> <p>Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance</p>
KPI	KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing
Test purpose	Test if the end-to-end reaction time from hazard detection at RSU until actuation/warning at CAV is enough.
Pre-test conditions	<p>Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.</p> <p>CAV operational in UC4 scenarios.</p> <p>PODIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational.</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">CAV, PODIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational</p> <p>Pedestrian (optionally equipped with V2X) at crossroads.</p>
Expected result (conformance requirements)	It is expected that for safety scenarios (VRU collision risk warning) the CAV is timely warned, conforming to the ETSI standard requirement for Intersection Collision Risk Warning (ICRW) application [ETSI TS 101 539-2 V1.1.1 (2018-06)].
Test procedure sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run scenarios based on DENM and CPM <p>Run scenarios of</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2 Straight warn (VRU violates red). 2.2 Right Turn with sudden crossing (VRU crosses). <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Consider the mean values of the five following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) At RSU, timing of VRU crossing detection application (2) Latency of RSU-MEC communication (3) at MEC, timing of digital twin and VIMA application (4) Latency of MEC-CAV communication (5) Timing of CAV application

	3. Sum the mean values to obtain an estimate of the end-to-end latency
Verification criteria	The derived end-to-end latency must be <300ms to confirm the expectation.

5.5. UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel

The UC5 covers a highway tunnel scenario. In this context, several things are going to be measured: the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the highway scenarios (inside the tunnel compared to outside), the accuracy in the vehicle counting by roadside sensors and CAV, and the capability of tracking V2X objects and fusing them with on board sensors if positioning worsens.

Table 30 Test case TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway
Context / Use Case	UC5 Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
KPI	KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway
Test purpose	Measure the positioning accuracy of the CAV throughout the highway scenarios, inside the tunnel, compared to outside
Pre-test conditions	CAV (and CV where applicable) operational in UC5 scenarios. A single technical solution for GNSS is operational in the tunnel: SDR or tri-lateration (they must NOT be available both at the same time). Infrastructure C-ITS warning messages available. Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	CAV is capable of self-localizing in-lane and the accuracy is sufficient for the use case purpose. A degradation performance is expected in the tunnel, sometimes yielding a positioning which is not at lane level. The latter situations are expected to impact considerably on C-ACC availability and on the ODD for AD L3 and L4 in presence of risk in the tunnel (DENM), less on the warning type scenario (scenarios 1.1, 2)
Test procedure sequence	Positioning is the focus of UC5 at CAV. This KPI is applicable to all scenarios: 1.1 RWW single vehicle 1.2 RWW and C-ACC follow 1.3 RWW and C-ACC cut-in 2 Traffic Jam Warning 3.1 AD keeps within ODD 3.2 AD exits the ODD Furthermore, each should be repeated in 4 different conditions: outside tunnel

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inside tunnel with no positioning infrastructure (dead reckoning at CAV, only) • inside tunnel with positioning infrastructure based on software defined radio (SDR) • inside tunnel with positioning infrastructure based on V2X (trilateration-based positioning) <p>Note: the two positioning solutions must be tested separate (only SDR or only trilateration).</p> <p>Procedure</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record positioning data along with the Use Case functionality data (e.g. manoeuvre, HMI, etc.). 2. Compute average positioning accuracy during scenario trials, Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle 3. Evaluate positioning accuracy results against use case functionality. <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>< 0.2m 95% of the time outside the tunnel with RTK correction < 1.5m 95% of the time outside the tunnel without RTK correction < 1.5m 95% inside the tunnel</p> <p>Percentage should be calculated over the samples in the test run, distinguishing inside from outside samples.</p> <p>Outlier cases (not passed) should be evaluated against use case functionality (along with context information, such as number of satellites, etc.) to check the causes, impact and whether some cases can be tolerated by the application.</p>

Table 31 Test case TC_KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Context / Use Case	UC5 Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
KPI	KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Test purpose	Measure the Accuracy % in the vehicles counting by roadside sensors
Pre-test conditions	CAV, CV and vehicle counting roadside sensors operational in UC5 scenarios. Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Vehicle counting is affected by the conditions but does not impact on risk management.
Test procedure sequence	This KPI is applicable to all scenarios: Procedure

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every time scenarios are run, record infrastructure counting 2. Compare measurements with the ground truth 3. Evaluate deviation effects against use case functionality <p>Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).</p>
<p>Verification criteria</p>	<p>< 10% deviations are the target. Higher deviations will be evaluated against use case functionality.</p>

Table 32 Test case TC_KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy

Test Case ID	TC_KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy
Context / Use Case	UC5 Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
KPI	KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Test purpose	Measure the Accuracy % in the vehicles counting by roadside sensors
Pre-test conditions	CAV and CV exchange detected vehicles in front through CPM. Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.
Expected result (conformance requirements)	Extended perception is degraded in GNSS denied environment, but the effect does not impact on cooperative and automated manoeuvres
Test procedure sequence	This KPI is applicable to the following scenarios: 3.1 AD keeps within ODD 3.2 AD exits the ODD Procedure <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Record CPM and detections by the on-board sensors. 2. Analyse object matching in the vehicle's LDM, selecting those objects that were detected both by communication (CPM) and by on board sensors. 3. Calculate the wrong/missed matches, against positioning accuracy degradation (confidence ellipse increasing) and communication lags (latency). Tests are executed in compliance with traffic regulations (respect of priority rules, speed limitations, road signalling, etc).
Verification criteria	Target value is < 10% deviation tolerance (V2V with respect to sensors) (the actual tolerance will be evaluated a posteriori, depending on the object tracking effectiveness which in turns depends on the detected cases).

6. User acceptance evaluation

This section describes the basic aspects of the PoDIUM user acceptance evaluation framework. The acceptance of the PoDIUM approach will be assessed via user acceptance surveys (questionnaire-based). Questionnaires will be structured in the form of multiple-choice questions to facilitate easy processing and analysis. The results will be collected and summarized in the form of user acceptance metrics.

To enlarge the target group beyond the participants to the PoDIUM trials, online feedback also from broader populations of interest will be pursued. Two types of surveys will be conducted, namely

- Surveys with representative trial users, i.e., test subjects taking part on the trials.
- Online surveys.

This deliverable exemplifies the user acceptance framework described in D2.3 for each of the survey types, detailing the KPIs that are going to be measured. As per Table 28 of D2.3 [7], the initially identified KPI categories for user acceptance are: intention to use, perceived usefulness, perceived ease-of-use, trust, reliability and privacy.

Social inclusion will be addressed as part of the evaluation of the usefulness for specific disadvantaged groups. Since, most probably, no members of a disadvantaged group will be participating as users in the trials, questions focusing on the specific needs of such groups will be included in the online surveys. The user acceptance evaluation methodology is based on the one used in the 5G-MOBIX [15] and 5G-IANA [13] projects. In the case of 5G-MOBIX, the objective was to evaluate the acceptance for the proposed CAM use cases including cross-border specifics. This is perfectly aligned with PoDIUM, with the clarification that the CCAM UCs considered in PoDIUM are very different and much more advanced than the ones of 5G-IANA. Notice that the 5G-MOBIX methodology has been significantly adapted to include i) recent developments on the field of user acceptance of CCAM, and ii) PoDIUM-specific aspects with privacy and trust being the most prominent such examples.

6.1. Overall methodology

User acceptance metrics assess the acceptability of a technology or service by potential users, focusing on their prospective judgment and actual adoption behaviour. Based on definitions by Shade and Schlag [16], acceptability is the anticipated judgment by users about adopting a technology, while acceptance is the actual adoption behaviour. PoDIUM, as an Innovation Action, aims to evaluate user acceptance under realistic trial conditions rather than demonstrating real-life adoption. The assessment will use user-acceptance models by Venkatesh et al. [17], which link acceptance to perceived usefulness and ease-of-use, but PoDIUM will also integrate factors such as trust, reliability, safety, and privacy into the user-acceptance model due to the safety-critical nature of the technologies being developed.

The evaluation model will incorporate constructs from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and extend them to include trust and perceived safety, along with system usability and user privacy. Metrics such as intention to use, perceived usefulness, ease-of-use, trust, reliability, and privacy will be measured using a psychometric scale composed of Likert-scale questions. Questionnaires will be tailored to different user types within PoDIUM, such as CAVs, CVs, normal vehicles, VRUs, and TMC

operators, ensuring relevance to each specific use-case. Despite logistical and safety constraints limiting trial participants, efforts will be made to increase the sample size by conducting multiple trials with different users and leveraging local test sites for pre-evaluation testing. This approach aims to enhance confidence in the findings by expanding the user base for more robust data collection.

Based on recent studies [18] social norm has been also identified as a key variable of user acceptance, especially regarding autonomous vehicles. Social norm (also appearing in literature as subjective norm or social influence) is the person’s perception that other important people in his social circle consider that this innovation should be adopted. In order to evaluate this metric, questions similar to the ones indicated in the Table below will be included in the questionnaire.

Table 33: Social norm as a user acceptance KPI category

KPI category	Indicative statements
Social norm	People whose opinions are important to me would also like the PoDIUM CAV.
	I would be proud to say to people that are close to me that I use a PoDIUM CAV.
	I would recommend the PoDIUM CAV to my family or friends to use.

A more detailed description of the overall methodology can be found in the deliverable D2.3. The resulting updated PoDIUM TAM is depicted below.

Figure 3 Updated PoDIUM Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to include social norm.

6.2. Survey with representative trial users

The actual PoDIUM users that will be participating in the trials (including any pre-evaluation testing) are the primary target group for the user acceptance evaluation. The following user types have been identified: drivers and passengers of CAVs, CVs, or normal vehicles, VRUs and the TMC operator.

After the completion of each trial or experiment, the participants will be asked to complete a questionnaire to assess the acceptance of the platform. The questionnaires will be adjusted to capture the aspects relative to the type of the PoDIUM user. Questionnaires will be adapted to evaluate those dimensions that can be judged from a potential user perspective.

The overall structure of questionnaire is described in the following sections.

6.2.1. Demographic data

The questionnaire starts with demographic data about the participants in the study, as shown in the Table below. Particular attention will be paid to the analysis of gender equality aspects, including proper representation in the sample.

Table 34 User demographic data

Question	Answer options
Gender	Female
	Male
	Prefer not to say / No answer
Age	<18
	18 to 25
	25 to 32
	32 to 40
	40 to 50
	>50
User type/role	Driver or passenger of CAV, CV, or normal vehicle, VRU or TMC operator
CCAM knowledge	5 or 6-point Likert scale.
Previous autonomous driving experience	Yes/No

6.2.2. User acceptance KPIs

All the initially identified KPI categories for user acceptance are applicable to trial users, namely intention to use, perceived usefulness, perceived ease-of-use, trust, reliability and privacy. The interested reader may find more details and indicative questions for the identified KPI categories on Table 28 of D2.3.

6.2.3. ATI scale

The questionnaire will also include a set of questions to assess the participant’s tendency to actively engage in intensive technology interaction, a factor that is known to affect acceptability. These questions are part of the Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI) scale, a widely used psychometric scale that evaluates a user’s proneness to interact with technological artefacts [19].

ATI scale consists of nine-items with each being answered in a 1 – 6 scale (1 – completely disagree; 6 – completely agree). The following items are part of the questionnaire:

1. I like to occupy myself in greater detail with technical systems.
2. I like testing the functions of new technical systems.
3. I predominantly deal with technical systems because I have to.
4. When I have a new technical system in front of me, I try it out intensively.
5. I enjoy spending time becoming acquainted with a new technical system.
6. It is enough for me that a technical system works; I don't care how or why.
7. I try to understand how a technical system exactly works.
8. It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system.
9. I try to make full use of the capabilities of a technical system.

For each individual, the final rating of the scale is obtained by inverting the answers of items (3,6,8) which imply a negative stance to technology and then computing a global mean.

6.3. Online survey

Given the difficulty in engaging a large number of participants in the actual trials, we intend to derive also insights from potential end-users via online questionnaires.

The online survey will be presenting in an easy to understand way the scenario under consideration, e.g., via a video that explains a specific PODIUM concept or UC. Video footage from the real trials will be used to ensure that a realistic experience. To increase engagement, the user will be able to experience each scenario from a different perspective, e.g., as a passenger, driver or simply as an observer.

After watching the video, the participants will complete a questionnaire, containing a carefully selected subset of the user acceptance questions (see trial users). All the questions will be answered using a Likert scale for ensuring privacy and easy/automated processing.

7. Conclusions

In this deliverable, PoDIUM's evaluation methodology is described, which has been developed to establish a common evaluation framework across the different living labs and use cases. This framework is intended for use not only by the use case demonstrations of the PoDIUM project partners but also by the agnostic testing of the PoDIUM platform.

The evaluation methodology is split into two parts: technical evaluation and user acceptance evaluation. The technical evaluation methodology is mainly based in the work done in ICT4CART and 5G-IANA projects. The PoDIUM KPIs were already defined in a previous D2.3 deliverable and an updated version is included in Annex 1. This deliverable builds upon that work and presents the concrete test cases that will be executed in the "Using" evaluation phase. The user acceptance methodology is mainly based in 5G-IANA and 5G-MOBIX, but adapted to the scope of PoDIUM, and involves questionnaires and representative user-focused and general online surveys.

With the delivery of the present document, the main milestone of the "Preparing" evaluation phase can be considered as completed. The next steps include preparing and coordinating the execution of the planned test cases, and finally analysing results and reporting conclusions.

Disclaimer of warranties

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

This project has adapted several methodologies already developed in previous projects: ICT4CART project (Grant Agreement number: 768953), 5G-MOBIX project (Grant Agreement number: 825496) and 5G-IANA project (Grant Agreement number: 101016427). Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for PoDIUM (Grant Agreement number: 101069547).

8. References

- [1] ARCADE, “FESTA Handbook Version 8,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/FESTA-Handbook-Version-8.pdf>.
- [2] ARCADE, “Micro-FESTA for CCAM pilot projects v2.0,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/micro-festa-v2/>.
- [3] C-ROADS Working Group 3 – Evaluation and Assessment, “Evaluation and Assessment Plan,” 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.c-roads.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/media/Dokumente/C-Roads_WG3_Evaluation_and_Assessment_Plan_version_1.2_December_2020.pdf.
- [4] ICT4CART, “D8.1 - Evaluation methodology,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5d1f4b746&appId=PPGMS>.
- [5] 5G-MOBIX, “D5.1 - Evaluation methodology and plan,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D5.1-Evaluation-methodology-and-plan-v1.0.pdf>.
- [6] 5G-IANA, “D5.2 - Validation methodology,” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/10533956>.
- [7] PoDIUM, “D2.3 - PoDIUM availability and cooperation enablers definition and evaluation data specifications,” 2023.
- [8] 3GPP, “User Equipment (UE) conformance specification (3GPP TS 38.523-1 V17.6.0),” 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/Specs/archive/38_series/38.523-1/38523-1-h60.zip.
- [9] FAME, “D4.2 - EU-CEM Handbook,” 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/EU-CEM-Handbook_DRAFT_240502.pdf.
- [10] PoDIUM, “D2.1 - PoDIUM use cases description and specifications,” 2023.
- [11] PoDIUM, “D2.2 - PoDIUM platform requirements and specifications,” 2023.
- [12] PoDIUM, “D3.1 - PoDIUM platform architecture description,” 2023.
- [13] 5G-IANA, “D5.1 - Initial validation KPIs and metrics,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/7304938#.Y6w6Z3bMJD9>.
- [14] 5G PPP Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation (TMV) Working Group, “White paper: Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values,” 2022. [Online]. Available: https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/white_paper_b5g-6g-kpis-camera-ready.pdf.
- [15] 5G-MOBIX, “D5.4 - Report on user acceptance,” 2022. [Online]. Available: https://5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-Mobix-D5.4-Report-on-User-Acceptance_V1.0_final.pdf.
- [16] J. a. S. B. Schade, “Acceptability of urban transport pricing strategies,” vol. 6, no. 1, 2003.
- [17] V. Venkatesh and H. Bala, “Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a Research Agenda on Interventions,” vol. 39, no. 2, 2008.
- [18] P. Jing, G. Xu, Y. Chen, Y. Shi and F. Zhan, “The Determinants behind the Acceptance of Autonomous Vehicles: A Systematic Review,” *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 1719, 2020.

- [1 C. A. a. D. W. T. Franke, “Personal Resource for Technology Interaction: Development and
9] Validation of the Affinity for Technology Interaction (ATI) Scale,” *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Interact.*,
vol. 35, no. 6, p. 456–467, 2019.

9. Annex 1: Updated version of KPIs

The initial version of the KPIs were included in the deliverable D2.3. For the present deliverable D5.1, all the KPIs included in D2.3 have been reviewed. As a consequence, some of the KPIs have been modified. For the convenience of the reader, this Annex 1 contains an updated version of the PoDIUM KPIs. The changes made are described at the beginning of each KPI category section.

9.1. Platform KPIs

Some minor changes have been made to the description of *KPI_P_2-updateLatency*. The rest of the KPIs remain the same.

Table 35 KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability

KPI identifier	KPI_P_1-serviceAvailability
Description	Service Availability, percentage of time the service is working with respect to the service being down; evaluated during demonstrations/experiments.
Context/Use Case	Platform, it applies to all computing entities that run services within use cases.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Logging/monitoring of services is necessary to know where the services are down and for how long. A set of acceptable causes of outages might be necessary, such as power outage, maintenance windows, etc. Monitoring might be done externally to services and every service is evaluated individually.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sum up of all the unacceptable outage time in logs obtain the elapsed working time (during experiments or demos) calculate the ratio and outage percentage.
How to Evaluate	Target Value range: > [95%, 99.5%]

Table 36 KPI_P_2-updateLatency

KPI identifier	KPI_P_2-updateLatency
Description	latency of update messages to the DT with sensors/collective perception/data. It is the time gap between the event detection and its availability in a service DT (in cloud or MEC servers)
Context/Use Case	Platform Applies to every update (in uplink), such as VRU crossing with incoming vehicle, sensor information updating digital twins.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	On MEC, Cloud computing entities
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors record timestamped events, such as road events, (i. e., the incoming of an emergency vehicle in UC2, or irregular crossing of VRU in UC4, or dangerous goods detection on UC5.)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The delays must be calculated between the nearest point of detection of the event and its reception timestamps into the MEC/Cloud DT that receives this data. A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.
How to Evaluate	The target values depend on the particular UC, since more responsive times are required for certain situations such as manoeuvre coordination and less responsive for traffic management. Target value range: < [50ms, 2.5s]

Table 37 KPI_P_3-notificationLatency

KPI identifier	KPI_P_3-notificationLatency
Description	latency of notification messages from a service in the platform (MEC, Cloud) to arrive to its final consumer (CV, VRU).
Context/Use Case	Platform. Any time gap from the generation of a warning/notification/indication to the final provision of indication to the CV, CAV, VRU
Where to observe/measure/monitor	On MEC/Cloud computing entities and message consumers (CV, VRUs, etc)
How to observe/measure/monitor	Analyze the messages generated within computing entities in the edge or cloud and those received in messages consumers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Notification transmission and consumption timestamps are recorded. The time gap between these two timestamps are the notification latency values. The consumption might occur in ADAS ECU, HMI, or Mobile terminal for VRUs. A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance over all the measurements represents the KPI value.
How to Evaluate	The target values depend on the particular UC. Target value range: < [50ms, 2.5s]

Table 38 KPI_P_4-processingDelay

KPI identifier	KPI_P_4-processingDelay
Description	The processing Time required between event (obstacle, VRU, road event) detection and the CCAM message availability for CAV to action, without accounting for transport delay.
Context/Use Case	Platform, in scenarios where road events are detected processed and transmitted to generate vehicle actions/notifications on CAVs, CVs and VRUs. It measures how fast the PDI generates notifications based on existing information, to be communicated to and consumed by users.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Within processing entities where the inputs from the road side are received and processed to produce an output notification.

How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timestamps during processing in services are necessary, that is, the timestamp when the triggering event was received by MEC/Cloud service and the timestamp of the warning/response/manoeuvre indication generated. • These time delays do not count delay due to transport. • A maximum value corresponding to the 95% percentile of acceptance is as the KPI value. •
How to Evaluate	<p>The target values depend on the particular UC, since more responsive times are required for certain situations such as manoeuvre coordination and less responsive for traffic management.</p> <p>Value range: < [50ms, 2.5s]</p>

Table 39 KPI_P_5-comReliability

KPI identifier	KPI_P_5-comReliability
Description	Communication message reliability. It describes how reliable is the PDI to deliver the messages to the users/vehicles/VRUs
Context/Use Case	Platform, in scenarios where redundant messages are sent with the same information in order to reach the target users/vehicles, and vice versa (from sensors/vehicles to edge/cloud).
Where to observe/measure/monitor	In vehicles, and computing entities sending and receiving CCAM messages.
How to observe/measure/monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logging the sending and reception of CCAM messages and comparing the amount of them with the sent messages for every sensor/RSU/vehicle/computing entity • A maximum value [or 95% percentile of acceptance] over all the measurements represents the KPI value. • It requires that endpoints are logging input and output CCAM messages and be able to identify them uniquely on both ends.
How to Evaluate	<p>The target values depend on the particular UC, since different reliability times are required for certain critical or non-critical situations.</p> <p>Target value range: > [90%, 99.99%]</p>

Table 40 KPI_P_6-SealedObject

KPI identifier	KPI_P_6-SealedObject
Description	This KPI represents the capability of the platform to protect sensible data/objects through the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and its sealing/unsealing features.
Context/Use Case	Platform
Where to observe/measure/monitor	OBU and RSU
How to observe/measure/monitor	Once the developers of the applications have defined the files to be protected, i.e., encrypted with a symmetric key stored into the TPM, the KPI is observed directly on OBU and RSU; sealed objects must be

	decrypted and used by applications running on OBU and RSU only in trusted states.
How to Evaluate	Testing the sealing and unsealing functions in different trusted and untrusted states. It must be possible to decrypt them for use only in trusted states; Target value > 99% successful tests.

Table 41 KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime

KPI identifier	KPI_P_7-LoadBootTime
Description	This KPI evaluate the boot time with and without the Software Integrity Architecture.
Context/Use Case	Platform in UC where software integrity is implemented
Where to observe/measure/monitor	OBU and RSU
How to observe/measure/monitor	This KPI is measured by taking the boot time of an OBU and RSU during all steps of the Bootstrap. The start time is defined by the act of power on and the end time by the OS login screen.
How to Evaluate	Evaluation is performed by comparing the boot time with and without Software Integrity Architecture and then calculating the difference in %. The increasing in boot time should be less than 30% Target value < 30% boot time increase

Table 42 KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime

KPI identifier	KPI_P_8-LoadRunTime
Description	This KPI evaluate the additional CPU utilization and memory consumption due to the Software Integrity Architecture.
Context/Use Case	Platform where software integrity is implemented
Where to observe/measure/monitor	OBU and RSU
How to observe/measure/monitor	This KPI is measured by running OBU and RSU common applications/services and recording the CPU load and memory consumption in the two configurations.
How to Evaluate	Comparing CPU load and memory consumption with and without the Software Integrity Architecture. CPU load in % and memory consumption in Byte or multiples; the differences are reported in % <i>and should be</i> Target value < 10% (CPU) and Target value < 20% (memory).

Table 43 KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation

KPI identifier	KPI_P_9-RemoteAttestation
Description	The Performance of the Remote Attestation protocol.
Context/Use Case	Platform where software attestation is implemented
Where to observe/measure/monitor	RSU and MEC

How to observe/measure/monitor	This KPI evaluates the performance of the Remote Attestation protocol as the latency between the start of communication between two nodes and the end of the protocol by calculating the time in seconds.
How to Evaluate	Protocol latency Target value < 3s.

9.2. Use Case KPIs

9.2.1. UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

There are no changes in UC1 KPIs. We paste here the content from D2.3 from the convenience of the reader.

Table 44 KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Maneuver-CAV

KPI identifier	KPI_UC1_1-Cooperative-Maneuver-CAV
Description	The CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative maneuver in at least 75% of the UC passes.
Context/Use Case	UC1
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At the living lab.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Qualitative evaluation of the traffic flow of the use case. An expert marks one pass through the UC as successful or not.
How to Evaluate	Calculate the percentage of passes considered successful over the total. Target value >75%

Table 45 KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Maneuver-VRU

KPI identifier	KPI_UC1_2-Cooperative-Maneuver-VRU
Description	The VRU on the free lane is able to pass the obstacle in a complex traffic situation without getting into a dangerous situation. Additionally, the CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre.
Context/Use Case	UC1
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At the living lab.
How to observe/measure/monitor	Qualitative evaluation of the traffic flow of the use case. An Expert marks one pass through the UC as successful or not.
How to Evaluate	Calculate the percentage of passes considered successful over the total. Target value >75%

9.2.2. UC2: PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

Four new KPIs have been added:

- KPI_UC2_4_EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction,
- KPI_UC2_5_EV_successful_coop_manoeuvres_percentage,
- KPI_UC2_6_VRU_collision_risk_reaction_time_reduction,
- KPI_UC2_7_VRU_collision_risk_reaction_softer_deceleration.

The rest of the KPIs remain the same.

Table 46 KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement

KPI identifier	KPI_UC2_1-Traffic_light_flow_improvement
Description	Percentage of times that EVs find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection.
Context/Use Case	UC2 Emergency vehicles (EVs) running through a corridor
Where to observe/measure/monitor	EV TMS or DT
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the logs of the EVs tracking functionality made by EV with the data for the status of traffic lights at each instant provided by TMS.
How to Evaluate	Calculation of the percentage of times that the traffic light is green when EVs reach a junction. Calculation of the same percentage calculated prior to the implementation of the connected EV tracking functionality. Calculate the percentage of the improvement rate with regards to tests prior to implementing the new functionality Target value > 25% improvement with regards to tests prior to implementing the new functionality

Table 47 KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD

KPI identifier	KPI_UC2_2-Percentage_trips_ok_OD
Description	Percentage of trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS
Context/Use Case	UC2 Calculation of O-D matrices
Where to observe/measure/monitor	CVs (or CAVs) TMS O-D calculation module
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the timestamps of the beginnings and ends of trips at CVs with the logs of the TMS => calculate the percentage of trips correctly processed
How to Evaluate	Target Percentage > 95%

Table 48 KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay

KPI identifier	KPI_UC2_3-Percentage_trips_ok_delay
Description	Percentage of travel times across road links correctly processed
Context/Use Case	UC2 Calculation of average delays and travel times across road links and/or crossing intersections
Where to observe/measure/monitor	CVs (or CAVs) TMS O-D calculation module
How to observe/measure/monitor	Comparison of the timestamps of the passing of through reference CVs with the logs of the TMS => calculate the percentage of trips correctly processed
How to Evaluate	Percentage > 95%

9.2.3. UC3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

There are no changes in UC3 KPIs. We copy here the content from D2.3 from the convenience of the reader.

Table 49 KPI_UC3_1-Service Time

KPI identifier	KPI_UC3_1-ServiceTime
Description	<p>Service delivery time (i.e. the reaction time at service layer) from time of incident detection or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, until incident notification of CVs and updated traffic instructions (“manoeuvres”) received by CVs. This KPI refers sets the “pace” of operation within the context of UC3. This time includes communication time, but also internal processing times, according to the following (successive) steps / milestones:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Traffic state perception update time: Period between successive updates of the traffic states generated from the Local TMC, using as input the fusion of data from different sources (traffic cameras, vehicle locations, obstacle/incident data). 4. Incident notification relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives an incident notification. 5. Traffic strategy decision time: Period to calculate and update the global traffic strategy within the Global TMC. 6. Strategy relay time: Time elapsed from the time of incident detection (or other strategy update trigger) until the moment the connected vehicle (CV or CAV) receives the updated TMC traffic strategy (manoeuvre instruction). This is the longest step.
Context/Use Case	Use case 3
Where to observe/measure/monitor	Local TMC (Edge), Global TMC (cloud), OBUs of the CAV/CVs
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>From the time of incident detection (as measured by the event timestamp within the MEC), or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, we will measure the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Traffic state perception update time: Measured via timestamps for each updated “traffic state” within the TMC. 4. Incident notification: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs). 5. Traffic strategy decision time: Measured via timestamps of the Traffic Strategies calculated, stored and emitted by the TMC. 6. Strategy relay: Measured through the timestamps in the message log of the vehicles (OBUs).
How to Evaluate	<p>Target values for end-to-end Service delivery / reaction times:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local traffic state perception updated within < 1s 2. Incident notification received by CAV/CVs in < 2s 3. Traffic strategy generation updated within < 5s 4. TMC strategy (manoeuvre instructions) received by CAV/CVs < 6s <p>Multiple measurements (> 10) will take place in virtual simulation (false triggers in pre-demonstration technical trials), where max values must be achieved every time.</p>

Table 50 KPI_UC3_2-Cross-Border Interruption Time

KPI identifier	KPI_UC3_2-CrossBorderInterruptionTime
Description	<p>Cross border interruption time (i.e. avoid interruption of service while switching from one country 5G network to the other)</p> <p>While crossing the France-Spain border, ensure that if connectivity via 5G is interrupted (due to switching from one country 5G network to the other), then this will be minimal, and be complemented via C-V2X coverage and will not cause any service interruption.</p>
Context/Use Case	Use case 3
Where to observe/measure/monitor	France-Spain cross-border segment of the LL highway
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measured through a tool that monitors and logs the connection state of the 5G modem.
How to Evaluate	<p>Target values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5G interruption from one country network to the other is < 1s Parallelization of C-V2X connection will allow to have continuous (seamless) connectivity without interruption → service interruption < 500ms <p>Measurements to take place during 5x cross border crossings with same or different CV/CAVs via connection monitor log software installed on the OBUs/PCs.</p>

Table 51 KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed

KPI identifier	KPI_UC3_3-ShuttleSpeed
Description	MILLA's CAV Shuttle needs to be capable to achieve 80km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.
Context/Use Case	Use case 3
Where to observe/measure/monitor	MILLA Shuttle CAV, in a closed circuit & in the selected highway section
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measured via the Shuttle's speed log. First, validated in closed circuit trials. Then this shall be demonstrated on a large stretch of the highway (traffic and safety permitting).
How to Evaluate	Target: 80 km/h automated driving

Table 52 KPI_UC3_4-Traffic Strategies Implementation

KPI identifier	KPI_UC3_4-TrafficStrategiesImplementation
Description	<p>Evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by the CAV (autonomously) and the CV drivers (manually).</p> <p>The referred traffic strategies that are transmitted to the vehicles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategy 1: Reduce max speed (thus avoiding a harder braking later on, increased safety) Strategy 2: Increase distance from car in front (thus avoiding harder braking, more time for reaction, increased safety) Strategy 3: Change lane i.e. the car should avoid or prefer such lane
Context/Use Case	Use case 3

Where to observe/ measure/ monitor	Within the vehicles (CV & CAV), and/or in the TMC/LDM
How to observe/ measure/ monitor	<p>Once the message is received by the vehicle (via OBU & displayed in the HMI), the CV drivers react based on the indicated strategy (“manoeuvre”) and the CAVs autonomously implement the indicated strategy.</p> <p>How to monitor:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capturing the timestamps of received messages in the OBU/PC and displayed in the HMI - Capturing by the logged speeds of the connected vehicles (CV & CAV), as stored in the TMC / LDM (for strategy 1 only)
How to Evaluate	<p>Target value:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delay of CAVs applying indicated strategy < 5s. - Delay of CV drivers applying indicated strategy < 10s <p>(Note: For lane change, this timing may be longer due to surrounding traffic – the manoeuvre will only take place once it is safe to do so.)</p> <p>For each strategy we will sample at least 3x times the manoeuvre with all 5 vehicles (CV and CAV) and calculate the time of reaction of the vehicles. In total 45 samples of all 3 strategy implementation manoeuvres.</p>

9.2.4. UC4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

The *KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_time_consistency* KPI has been replaced by *KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization*. In addition, some minor changes have been applied to the description of *KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance* and *KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing*.

Table 53 *KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_performance*

KPI identifier	KPI_UC4_1-VIMA_detection_performance
Description	Performance of VRU Intersection Movement Assist (VIMA) application against false positive/negative
Context/Use Case	In UC4, the VIMA application provides the connected and automated vehicle/driver with a warning and a time window to wait, based on VRU detection. Reliability of this service will be assessed.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At CAV
How to observe/measure/monitor	<p>Perform use case in different scenarios/trials with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - expected positive= scenarios in which the system is expected to give a warning and a time to wait indication because the VRU is about to cross and conflicting with vehicle trajectory - expected negative= scenarios in which the system should NOT give any warning or indication because VRU is not about to cross or not conflicting with vehicle trajectory (tested to check for any false warning) <p>Collect data and check true positive/ negative, false positive/negative.</p>
How to Evaluate	<p>Compute the following performance indicators (PI) and compare it with target values.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PI1: true positive rate (probability of detection): true positives over total expected positives - PI2: true negative rate (1-false positive rate) is the number of true negative over total expected negatives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the current prototype implementation, the target is to have at least 90% of each PI, which in practice means a tolerance of 10% error.

Table 54 *KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban*

KPI identifier	KPI_UC4_2-Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban
Description	CAV positioning accuracy at the intersection
Context/Use Case	UC4 advisory depends on lane-level position and direction, thus matching of vehicle position and trajectory to the local topology is crucial. Lane level accuracy (1.5m) is at least needed to interpret the advisory information, but sub-meter accuracy (0.1m, 0.2m tolerated) is recommended for collective perception applied to highly automated driving.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At CAV

How to observe/measure/monitor	Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle (both receiving and transmitting) within 2 sigma (95%) in open sky, with at least 7 satellites in view, and elevation mask set to 5°.
How to Evaluate	Accuracy: < 0.2m with RTK correction < 1.5m without RTK correction

Table 55 KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization

KPI identifier	KPI_UC4_3-VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization
Description	VIMA suggestions should lead to optimal manoeuvres to cross the intersection,..
Context/Use Case	UC4 VIMA application provides warning and a time window to wait based on VRU detection. The hypotheses are that, with Podium system active (with respect to inactive) the vehicle: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • should react in advance (start deceleration manoeuvre). • should wait a similar time slot • should have a smoother speed profile In the Living Lab manoeuvres will be addressed with manual driving and HMI recommendations.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At CAV
How to observe/measure/monitor	Baseline: VRU crossing trial with system on, no HMI. Podium system runs in background in order to record the scene (vehicle and VRU crossing). Treatment: VRU crossing trial with Podium system on and HMI with driving recommendation (which would mean CAV actuation). This is applicable to all scenarios involving VIMA IVIM (which include the information that a VRU is crossing). Measure and compare baseline/treatment.
How to Evaluate	Evaluation based on baseline vs treatment comparison. In particular, Podium system should yield:< +/-20% deviation in total time to cross > 10% reaction time advance (treatment/baseline) > 10% reduction in maximum acceleration/deceleration values

Table 56 KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing

KPI identifier	KPI_UC4_4-VIMA_timing
Description	End-to-end reaction time from VRU collision risk detection at RSU until notification at CAV.
Context/Use Case	UC4 VIMA, an edge-computing-based application informing of VRU presence at an intersection, should at least perform as good as an Intersection Collision Risk Warning (ICRW) application, as in ETSI TS 101 539-2 V1.1.1 (2018-06).
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At all the involved components
How to observe/measure/monitor	Reaction time will be measured from timestamps. Since the tracking of each piece of information at each step may be difficult to achieve, the

	<p>mean values of the five following steps will be measured and then summed up:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">(1) At RSU, timing of VRU crossing detection application(2) Latency of RSU-MEC communication(3) at MEC, timing of digital twin and VIMA application(4) Latency of MEC-CAV communication(5) Timing of CAV application
How to Evaluate	<p>Target: < 300ms</p> <p>The aforementioned ETSI document sets a requirement of 300ms delay overall as maximum. Transposed to VIMA, for comparison, the sum of steps 1 to 5 above should not exceed 300ms.</p>

9.2.5. UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel

KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_position_timing_transient has been replaced with KPI_UC5_3-Vehicle_perception_accuracy. The description of KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy has been extended to add more detail. KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway remains the same.

Table 57 KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway

KPI identifier	KPI_UC5_1-Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway
Description	CAV positioning accuracy on the highway
Context/Use Case	UC5 warning and cooperative assistive/automated functions (e.g. C-ACC) can be defined up to the lane-level, along the highway (e.g. lane closure information). The CAV must be capable of understanding which lane it finds itself, meaning positioning has to be <1.5m. Furthermore, outside the tunnel, the CAV can avail of sub-meter accuracy thanks to RTK corrections. Sub meter accuracy (0.1m -0.2m tolerated) is one of the enabling factors of highly automated driving Operational Design Domain (ODD).
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At CAV
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measure positioning accuracy of the vehicle (both receiving and transmitting) within 2 sigma (95%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in open sky, with at least 7 satellites in view, and elevation mask set to 5° • in tunnel with the two positioning solutions (trilateration and GPS signal creation)
How to Evaluate	Target Value: < 0.2m outside the tunnel with RTK correction < 1.5m outside the tunnel without RTK correction < 1.5m inside the tunnel

Table 58 KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy

KPI identifier	KPI_UC5_2-Vehicle_counting_accuracy
Description	Accuracy % in the vehicles counting by entities that have this capability in Podium UC5
Context/Use Case	UC5 aims at improving the Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel. Among the monitoring sources, dedicated vehicle counters developed within the Project are installed in the tunnel and interfaced with the Digital twin system, to support the Risk Assessment module. Vehicles are counted and classified by its category (motorbike, car, bus or truck). Furthermore, vehicles are equipped with sensors detecting other road users. While the detection itself is not affected by the tunnel, when the vehicles' position comes into play, the lack of GNSS is expected to have an impact., for instance when matching objects of CPM received with the same objects detected by sensors (an object may be counted twice if not correctly matched).

Where to observe/measure/monitor	At MEC and back-end
How to observe/measure/monitor	Measure vehicle counting e.g. in one hour at the tunnel. Compare it to the measurement of the system already in place on the A22. Calculate the deviation target.
How to Evaluate	Target value: < 10% deviation per each category

Table 59 KPI_UC5_3-Vehicle_perception_accuracy

KPI identifier	KPI_UC5_3-Extended_perception_accuracy
Description	Accuracy in perceiving vehicles in front
Context/Use Case	Vehicles are equipped with sensors detecting other road users. CAV and CV exchange detected vehicles in front through CPM. GNSS degradation as well as V2V communication latency is expected to have an impact, when matching/tracking objects of CPM received with the same objects detected by sensors.
Where to observe/measure/monitor	At CAV/CV
How to observe/measure/monitor	Compare received CPM measurement with sensors object coordinates. Calculate the deviation against positioning accuracy degradation (confidence ellipse increasing) and communication lags (latency). Check the capability of object tracking by the data fusion module, depending on the deviation. Perform multiple tests over several traffic conditions, to obtain a significant and diversified number of cases.
How to Evaluate	Target value: < 10% deviation tolerance (V2V with respect to sensors) (the actual tolerance will be evaluated a posteriori, depending on the object tracking effectiveness which in turns depends on the detected cases).